

MAIN PROBLEMS OF NOMINATION AND ANTHROPONYMS IN MODERN LINGUISTICS

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Abstract. *The article studies the linguistic features of anthroponyms as units of language and units of intercultural communication. The article considers a look at the history of the emergence and development of English anthroponyms, the definition of their types and properties, and determines the methods of transferring anthroponyms within the framework of intercultural and interlingual communication.*

Key words: *anthroponym, onomastics, nomination, intercultural communication, interlingual communication, linguistic unit.*

ОСНОВНЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ НОМИНАЦИИ И АНТРОПОНИМОВ В СОВРЕМЕННОМ ЯЗЫКОЗНАНИИ

Аннотация. *В статье исследуются языковые особенности антропонимов как единиц языка и единиц межкультурной коммуникации. В статье рассматривается взгляд на историю возникновения и развития английских антропонимов, определение их видов и свойств, а также определяются способы передачи антропонимов в рамках межкультурной и межъязыковой коммуникации.*

Ключевые слова: *антропоним, ономастика, номинация, межкультурная коммуникация, межъязыковая коммуникация, языковая единица.*

INTRODUCTION

The growing interest in the problems of names has been manifested in various areas of linguistics in recent decades. Proper names are included as an integral and most essential part of the class of names. Their specificity has been recognized for a long time, but so far, the peculiarities of the use of names in various contexts remain unexplored. The interpretation of such fundamental points as the meaning of personal names and their classification is disputable. The possibility of conscious, exclusive regulation by native speakers in the field of personal names can, to a certain extent, demonstrate the processes and mechanisms of nomination. Nomination - naming objects and situations with the help of linguistic means, assigning to a specific referent.

Onomastics comes from the Greek word *onomastike* that is, the art of naming. The term "onym" (*onoma*, proper name) is a word or phrase that serves to highlight the object it names among other objects: its individualization and identification. Onomastics explores phonetic, morphological, derivational, semantic, etymological and other aspects of proper names.

An anthroponym is a proper name (or a set of names, including all possible variants), officially assigned to an individual as his identification mark. The anthroponym names, but does not attribute any properties. Anthroponyms have a conceptual meaning, which is based on the idea of a category, a class of objects. This value usually has the following features:

a) an indication that the bearer of the anthroponym is a person: Peter, Lewis in contrast to London, Thames;

b) an indication of belonging to a national linguistic community: Robin, Henry, William, in contrast to Reni, Henri, Wilhelm;

c) an indication of the person's gender: John, Henry as opposed to Mary, Elizabeth.

Anthroponyms especially a personal name, differs from many other IS (onyms) in the nature of the individualization of the object: each object of the nomination (person) has a name. Anthroponyms like any onyms is not only a linguistic, but also a socio-historical entity that functions under special conditions as a necessary element of human communication.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

It is clear that each person cannot have a unique, only inherent name for him. Both personal names and surnames, taken by themselves, have many carriers. Outside of a specific situation or sphere of communication, the names John, Elizabeth, Thomas, etc. do not point to any particular person. Such names, which in the linguistic consciousness of the collective are not preferably associated with any one person, we will call multiple anthroponyms. Other anthroponyms also belong to many people, but are primarily associated with one person. These are the names of people who have gained wide popularity (Plato, Shakespeare, Darwin, Einstein, etc.). V.P. Berkov proposed to distinguish between these groups, respectively, as general and individual.

Thus, it is necessary to differentiate the concepts of "single anthroponym" and "multiple anthroponym". For single anthroponyms, in addition to the features characteristic of both types, information about the bearer of the name is important. In addition, in a situation where the text does not contain an object indicated by an anthroponym, and the text itself is intended, among other things, for an international audience, additional information about this object may be necessary.

The concept of a personal name, i.e. the attitude of the members of the language community to their names is gradually changing, and this leads to the restructuring of anthroponymic systems. For a modern English person, the most natural two-component naming. It can be: name + name + surname; name + nickname. Since the 1990s, two-component naming has begun to spread in business and political circles, consisting of the full form of the name and surname. In previous eras, this method of naming was used only in the artistic environment.

For anthroponomy, the categories of diminutiveness and endearment are of particular importance (in English grammars they are sometimes combined). Words expressing diminutives are called deminutives, and hypocoristics express petting - when naming a person or any other animate or inanimate objects. For example, a mountain (large) is a hill (small), and a hill, a gorushka are affectionate words; bear (big), bear, bear cub (small), Medvedushka, Medvedko - affectionate names of a bear or appeal to a bear. As a result of deminutivation, the names of other objects can be created: a hand - a handle (doors), a leg - a leg (beds), an eagle - an eagle (a bird of another detachment). In English anthroponymy, since ancient times, deminutivation has been used to name children: they were given the name of the parent in a diminutive form (vertical structural co-naming).

CONCLUSION

Based on the studied material, the following conclusions can be drawn: The ethics of intercultural communication determines the use of anthroponyms. Name forms can be influenced by a person's position in society, his age, types of social formations (army, professional circles), size and type of society (city, village, country), adopted passport rules and life situations.

Different modes of address serve as ways of positioning a person at different levels of society: in the family, community, work or service, even internationally. Thus, a certain system of names is being formed, in which one can distinguish: respectful, dismissive, affectionate, official, neutral and other appeals and naming. The speakers of the English-speaking culture are quite aware of the naming system in the English language. This allows the translation to do without additional explanations (often the lack of special explanations is compensated by the linguistic context, which expands to several sentences). On the other hand, such a bold use of various diminutive forms noted by us raises doubts, since it significantly complicates the perception of the text, and, consequently, the very process of intercultural communication, in which the English-speaking reader is involved. It seems that addressing and naming with explanations of a different nature are more effective in the process of intercultural communication.

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